

Relative reactivities of glucopyranosides towards permanganate and chromic acid in perchloric acid medium

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The oxidative behaviour and relative reactivity of methyl- α -D-glucopyranoside and methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside towards permanganate and acid chromate have been studied in perchloric acid medium. The reactions are first order with respect to [glucopyranoside] and [oxidant]. The reaction rates increase with the increase in $[H^+]$. Activation parameters of the reactions have been evaluated. The mechanism of the reactions has been discussed.

Glycosides are usually associated with enzymes which occur in different cells of the plant¹. Anthocyanins which are natural plant pigments containing glycosides are responsible for large variety of colours in flowers. Most glycosides which generally exist as β -D-glucopyranoside occur in nature. From the knowledge of enzyme hydrolysis it is found that α -D-glucose is stereochemically related to methyl- α -D-glucoside and β -D-glucose to methyl- β -D-glucoside. There are no systematic data involving the oxidative behaviour of methyl glucopyranosides towards metal ion oxidants although oxidations of aldoses by different oxidants have been studied².

The present report deals with the oxidative behaviour and relative reactivity of methyl- α -D- and β -D-glucopyranosides towards permanganate and chromic acid in perchloric acid medium.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants obtained in the oxidation of methyl- α -D-glucopyranoside and methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside by Mn^{VII} are $(1.82 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-4}$ and $(1.92 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ at [glucopyranoside] = $8.0 \times 10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}$, $[Mn^{VII}] = (3.3-33.3) \times 10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 2 mol dm^{-3}$ at 303 K, whereas those by Cr^{VI} are $(4.8 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-4}$ and $(5.45 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, respectively at [glucopyranoside] = $1.33 \times 10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}$, $[Cr^{VI}] = (0.55-4.4) \times 10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 2 mol dm^{-3}$ at 308 K. The results indicate that the rate is first order with respect to each [oxidant]. The pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase in [glucopyranoside] but at constant [oxidant], $[H^+]$ and temperature. The results (Fig. 1) indicate that each reaction is first order with respect to [glucopyranoside].

The influence of acidity on the reaction rates was investigated at different hydrogen ion concentrations but at constant ionic strength (μ) of $3.02 mol dm^{-3}$ and $3.83 mol dm^{-3}$ for the oxidation by Mn^{VII} and Cr^{VI} , respectively. Ionic

Fig. 1. Plots of k_{obs} against [glucopyranoside] for (i) oxidation by acid permanganate : $[Mn^{VII}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 2 mol dm^{-3}$, temp. = 303 K; (ii) oxidation by chromic acid $[Cr^{VI}] = 1.67 \times 10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 2 mol dm^{-3}$, temp. 308 K.

strength was adjusted by the addition of sodium perchlorate. The reaction rate increases with increase in $[H^+]$ (Table 1). An attempt was made to correlate the acid dependence using $[H^+]$ and also Hammett acidity function. The plots of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $-H_o$ (where H_o is the Hammett acidity function) are linear in the acid range $1.33-3.33 mol dm^{-3}$. The slopes of the plots are less than unity, which are 0.56 and 0.6 for the oxidations of α -D-glucopyranoside and β -D-glucopyranoside by Mn^{VII} , respectively; the same with the other oxidant are 0.88 and 0.8, respectively. The values of $-H_o$ at various acidities are taken from the table of Paul and Long. However, when $\log k_{obs}$ was plotted against $\log [H^+]$, a linear relationship was obtained in the entire range

of acidity ($0.33\text{--}3.33\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ has been calculated from the slopes of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ plots, which are 1.4 and 1.5 for the α - and β -compound, respectively, whereas the respective values in the oxidation by Cr^{VI} are 2.0 and 1.9.

Table 1. Variation of pseudo-first order rate constants with HClO_4 concentration for the oxidations of glucopyranosides by Mn^{VII} and Cr^{VI}

(a) $[\text{Glucopyranoside}] = 1 \times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}] = 1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 3.02\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 303 K

(b) $[\text{Glucopyranoside}] = 1.33 \times 10^{-2}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 1.67 \times 10^{-3}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 3.83\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 308 K

$[\text{HClO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	(a)		(b)	
	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}
0.33	0.31	0.39	0.23	0.38
0.67	0.94	1.02	1.28	1.51
1.33	2.51	2.95	4.67	6.6
2.00	4.36	5.49	10.9	13.8
2.67	6.61	8.51	21.7	24.0
3.33	9.12	11.9	37.1	39.8

The second order rate constants (k_2) for the reactions have been determined at different temperatures. Enthalpies of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) were calculated from the plots of $\log(k_2/T)$ vs $1/T$ followed by activation entropies (ΔS^\ddagger) (Table 2). The activation parameters obtained in the oxidations of the substrates by each oxidant are not widely different, indicating that similar mechanism may be operative in these reactions.

Table 2. Activation parameters of different reactions at $[\text{HClO}_4] = 2\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Substrate	Mn^{VII}		Cr^{VI}	
	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{JK}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{JK}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$
Methyl- α -D-glucopyranoside	51	-110	67	-53
Methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside	58	-83	69	-46

The first order rate constants³ for the acid-catalysed hydrolysis of methyl- α -D-glucopyranoside and methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside in 2.0 mol dm^{-3} HCl are respectively 0.708×10^{-5} and $1.26 \times 10^{-5}\text{ s}^{-1}$ at 333 K. Thus hydrolysis of the glucopyranoside followed by oxidation of the products may be neglected. The rate of oxidation of the glucopyranosides by these oxidants are not widely different although the results indicate that the β -compound is oxidised at slightly faster rate than the α -compound. These indicate that similar mechanism may be operative in all these cases of oxidation. Moreover, C-1 has been shown to be more reactive than C-6 possibly because C-1 has a potential CHO group⁴ unlike C-6 which possesses a CH_2OH

group. On the other hand, when C-1 and C-6 are blocked by phosphate group, C-2, C-3 and C-4 are not easily oxidised⁴ by different oxidants in acid medium. The reactive site of the methyl glucopyranosides is believed to be C-6 since C-1 is blocked by the methyl group. Since both the oxidants are fully protonated, the higher order with respect to $[\text{H}^+] > 1$ may be explained as due to the protonation of the substrates also. Different values obtained with α - and β -compound are due to the spatial arrangement of the substrates which are also different. The activation parameters obtained are not widely different from those of the oxidation of alcohols by these oxidants in acidic medium⁵. It seems probable that protonated glucopyranosides react with the protonated oxidants to give intermediate esters (fast step) which subsequently break down to give products (slow step). The reaction steps involving protonated methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside and oxidants are shown in Scheme 1.

Thus CH_2OH group of the glucopyranosides are oxidised to give CHO group. The literature evidence⁶ also indicates the presence of an aldehyde group at C-6 of methyl- β -glucopyranoside. However, the concentration of aldehyde compounds are much smaller as compared to those of the parent glucopyranosides and hence further oxidation of the aldehyde compounds will be insignificant under the conditions at which the present kinetic experiments were carried out.

In the oxidation of glucopyranosides by permanganate, Mn^{VII} is reduced to Mn^{V} . Since the reaction mixtures failed to give precipitation of MnO_2 , the Mn^{V} formed disproportionates to give Mn^{VII} and Mn^{II} ⁷. In the oxidation of the glucopyranosides by Cr^{VI} , the latter is reduced to Cr^{IV} . Chromium(IV) generated in the rate-determining step being unstable, readily disproportionates⁸ or reacts rapidly with Cr^{VI} to give Cr^{V} ⁹. The latter finally reacts with the glucopyranosides in fast steps to give the products, and Cr^{V} is reduced to Cr^{III} .

Experimental

Methyl- α -D-glucopyranoside (Koch-Light) and methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside (Fluka), potassium permanganate,

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potassium dichromate (both AnalaR) and perchloric acid (E. Merck) were used. All materials were of the highest purity available. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

The kinetics were followed by removing aliquots at suitable intervals of time, followed by estimation of the unreacted Mn^{VII} and Cr^{VI} titrimetrically. Kinetics runs in the oxidation of permanganate were performed in presence of $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ sodium fluoride in order to suppress the intermediate valence state of manganese¹⁰. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated from the slopes ($r > 0.98$) of $\log [\text{Mn}^{\text{VII}}]$ or $\log [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ vs time plots. Duplicates were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

The α - and β -methylglucopyranosides are oxidized by periodate to give dialdehyde¹¹ type of products and also one carbon atom of the carbohydrate is lost as formaldehyde or formic acid. It has also been shown that the optical rotation of the products of oxidation decreased considerably from those of the parent substrates. In the present reactions, the optical rotations of the parent substrates and those of the oxidation products were measured which remained to be same. These indicate that dialdehyde type of products are not formed rather CH_2OH group at C-6 is oxidized to CHO. The reaction mixtures after kinetic experiments were made alkaline by the addition of requisite amount of sodium hydroxide. To the alkaline solutions when ammoniacal silver nitrate was added, a silver mirror was produced in each reaction¹². Similar experiments using authentic glucopyranosides failed to respond such test.

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References

- 1 I L Finar, "Organic Chemistry", 5th ed, ELBS, Singapore, Vol II
- 2 K K Sen Gupta and S N Basu, *Carbohydr Res*, 1979, **72**, 139, 1980, **80**, 223, 1980, **86**, 7, K K Sen Gupta, S Sen Gupta and S N Basu, *Carbohydr Res*, 1979, **71**, 75
- 3 B Capon, *Chem Rev*, 1969, **69**, 421
- 4 K K Sen Gupta, S Sen Gupta, S K Mandal and A Mahapatra, *J Chem Res (S)*, 1969, 60
- 5 K K Banerji, *Bull Chem Soc Jpn*, 1973, **46**, 3623, J Rocek and F H Westheimer, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1962, **84**, 2241
- 6 O Theander, *Acta Chem Scand*, 1964, **18**, 1297
- 7 L I Simandi and M Jaky, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1976, **98**, 1995
- 8 G P Haight, T Huang and B Shakhshiri, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1971, **33**, 2169
- 9 J N Copper, G E Standt, M L Smalser, L M Setzso and G P Haight, *Inorg Chem*, 1973, **12**, 2075
- 10 R M Barter and J S Littler, *J Chem Soc (B)*, 1967, 205
- 11 K B Wiberg, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Academic, London, 1965, Part A
- 12 A I Vogel, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed, ELBS, London, 1980